

GIARDIASIS'S CAUSES, SYMPTOMS AND ITS PREVENTION

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Annotation

Giardia is a tiny parasite (germ) that causes the diarrheal disease giardiasis. *Giardia* is found on surfaces or in soil, food, or water that has been contaminated with feces (poop) from infected people or animals. *Giardia* spreads easily and can spread from person to person or through contaminated water, food, surfaces, or objects. The most common way people get sick is by swallowing contaminated drinking water or recreational water (for example, lakes, rivers, or pools).

Key words: *Giardia lamblia*, parasites, enteroscopy, fatigue, nausea, diarrhea, abdominal cramps, weight loss.

Giardiasis is an infection in your small intestine. It's caused by a microscopic parasite called *Giardia lamblia*. Giardiasis spreads through contact with infected people. And you can get giardiasis by eating contaminated food or drinking contaminated water. Pet dogs and cats also frequently contract giardia. This condition can be found all over the world, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). However, it's more common in overcrowded developing countries that lack sanitary conditions and water quality control. *Giardia lamblia* are found in animal and human feces. These also thrive in contaminated food, water, and soil, and can survive outside a host for long periods of time. Accidentally consuming these parasites can lead to an infection. The most common way to get giardiasis is to drink water that contain *Giardia lamblia*. Contaminated water can be in swimming pools, spas, and bodies of water, such as lakes. Sources of contamination include animal feces, diapers, and agricultural

runoff. Contracting giardiasis from food is less common because heat kills the parasites. Poor hygiene when handling food or eating produce rinsed in contaminated water can allow the parasite to spread. Giardiasis also spreads through personal contact. For example, unprotected anal sex can pass the infection from one person to another. Changing a child's diaper or picking up the parasite while working in a day care center are also common ways to become infected. Children are at high risk for giardiasis because they're likely to encounter feces when wearing diapers or potty training.

You may have to submit one or more stool samples for testing. A technician will check your stool sample for giardia parasites. You could have to submit more samples during treatment. Your doctor may also perform an enteroscopy. This procedure involves running a flexible tube down your throat and into your small intestine. This will allow your doctor to examine your digestive tract and take a tissue sample. Some people can carry giardia parasites without experiencing any symptoms. Symptoms of giardiasis generally show up one or two weeks after exposure. Common symptoms include: fatigue, nausea, diarrhea or greasy stools, loss of appetite, vomiting, bloating and abdominal cramps, weight loss, excessive gas, headaches, abdominal pain.

In most cases, giardiasis eventually clears up on its own. Your doctor might prescribe medication if your infection is severe or prolonged. Most doctors will recommend treatment with antiparasitic drugs, rather than leaving it to clear up on its own. Certain antibiotics are commonly used to treat giardiasis:

Metronidazole is an antibiotic that needs to be taken for five to seven days. It can cause nausea and leave a metallic taste in your mouth .

Tinidazole is as effective as metronidazole, and often treats giardiasis in a single dose.

Nitazoxanide is a popular option for children because it's available in liquid form and only needs to be taken for three days.

Paromomycin has a lower chance of causing birth defects than other antibiotics, although pregnant women should wait until after delivery before taking any medication for giardiasis. This medication is given in three doses over the course of 5 to 10 days.

To help prevent the spread of giardia, always practice good personal hygiene, for example:

Wash hands properly, especially after going to the toilet, before handling food and after every nappy change.

Do not share linen, towels or eating utensils with other people who have symptoms.

Boil water before drinking if you suspect contamination.

Keep infected people from childcare, pre-school, school or work until they have not had any diarrhoea for at least 24 hours.

Do not use swimming pools for at least 2 weeks after diarrhoea has completely stopped.

All in all, giardiasis is an infectious disease, measures aimed at preventing its spread are important. This puts several tasks before hygienists and doctors. It is very important for us to observe the rules of personal hygiene, wash and eat fruits and vegetables.

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